

Article

Muslim Students' Access to Mobile Phone

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Abstract

Learning through mobile phone has facilitated the students to acquire knowledge-on-the-go. As a result, accessing mobile phone is not hindered by the family income but, even there is perceived variation of the level of adoption in terms of gender, age, class, religion, income and occupation. This paper examines the mobile phone access patterns perceived among the rural female Muslim women in India. The paper is based on the empirical data collected by administering a structured interview schedule to a stratified random sample of the rural female Muslim students studying in higher educational institutions of the Silchar town in south Assam.

Key words: Muslim women, rural students, higher education, mobile phone access.

Introduction

Human beings live in a geographically dispersed complex world. It is necessary to maintain a significant proportion of the social network across time and space where opportunities for face-to-face meetings are intermittent. Telephone, particularly mobile phone, enables them to participate without hindrances in a set of relationships in this complex social world.

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This new communication technology has influenced the social, cultural and political processes. The social history of mobile phone involves both the history of technological development and an account of changing social and political frameworks into which the new technological developments become integrated.

Though the technological innovations of mobile telephony were established in the 1940s its adoption could not take off until the 1990s. It has been claimed that the mobile telephone revolution can be explained by changes in the way communication happens through social networks, different from old hierarchical forms (Lacohée & Pearson., 2003, pp. 203-211). Mobile telephone has been “....a way of rebuilding economies in Eastern Europe, an instrument of unification in Western Europe, a fashion statement in Finland or Japan, a mundane means of communication in the USA ... an agent of political change in the Philippines....” (Agar, . 2003.) Mobile phone has recently emerged as the first extensive form of new communication technology in India. It is cheaper than landline telephones, and the communication through mobile phone does not require much literacy ever since the introduction of mobile phone technology in 1995. People owning mobile phone in India and China are more than their counterparts in North America and Europe combined. Mobile phones have a number of important characteristics which make them attractive from educational perspective. These include increasing portability, functionality, multimedia convergence, ubiquity, personal ownership, social interactivity, context sensitivity, location awareness, connectivity and personalisation (Pachler, 2010.). A mobile phone is not a luxury anymore, it is a necessity. The mobile learning refers to the exploitation of ubiquitous handheld technologies, together with wireless and mobile phone networks, to facilitate, support, enhance and extend the reach of teaching and learning. The Third generation

(3G) mobile technology incorporates voice data and Internet access, making smart phones similar to personal computers. Mobile technologies have considerable potential to enhance teaching and learning across all educational sectors. Their impact on students' behaviour, enthusiasm, motivation and progress is well-documented (Attewell, 2005).(Murat, 2008.). A study (Jambulingam, 2013.) of 351 participants from private universities conducted to know the factors that influence the behavioural intention of the adoption of Mobile Technology in the Learning Environment (MTLE) of Malaysia by adopting the Modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model found that performance expectancy, affordability and pedagogy had a significant impact on students' adoption of MTLE, without a significant effect of both age and gender as moderators, and it also proposed the incorporation of such technology into the educational environment of students and universities. Micro-entrepreneurial training in marketing and mobile phone sets given to women in Chennai, India, by the Foundation of Occupational Development (FOOD) has increased women's earnings and empowered them to take new initiatives (Loyola 2005). Age of the students is a factor in determining patterns of using the mobile phone. Younger students are more inclined to use the additional features of the mobile phone, such as MMS and GPRS while older users prefer to use the conventional voice calls. The amount of time spent on and the enthrallment with features of mobile phone easily attract students to and obsess them with the mobile phone. Female students use the SMS feature more than male students who are more interested with other technological features of the mobile phone. Besides, students frequently contact their friends more compared to their parents (Zulkefely, 2009). Technical applications of mobile phone like MP3 players attract more male users while mobile phone was a mere tool of mingling with friends and relatives for female users. Females use the mobile phone for social reasons while males call more people on a regular basis. Older persons use mobile phone more for business purposes while younger students use it for socialisation and they are more obsessed to mobile phone's use (Bianchi, 2005).

Thus, mobile phone is more accessible and less expensive means of communication among users of different genders, age groups, and educational, occupational and income levels. Muslims constitute a religious minority in India in accordance with the principles laid down in the Constitution of India. Besides minority status, gender and rural- urban residence influence the access of people to mobile telephony in India. Thus, a question arises: What mobile phone access patterns are perceived among the rural female Muslim students in India, especially Assam- a remote state located in its northeastern region? The question is attempted with reference to higher educational institutions (six colleges, a university and a National Institute of Technology) of Silchar town in South Assam. The field data used in the paper were collected during the period from 14th February 2011 – 29th February 2012, by administering a structured interview schedule to a stratified random sample of 144 female Muslim students of rural background studying in these institutions.

Silchar Town

Silchar town is the locus of the administrative headquarters of the Cachar district. Its geographical area is 15.78 sq. kms with a population of 1, 72, 709: males-86,812 (50.26%) and females- 85,897 (49.74%). The sex ratio in the town is 989 females per '000 males. Educationally, total literates in the town are 1, 44, 255 (91.74%): males- 74,082 (93.97%) and females- 70,173 (89.5%) (Govt of India 2011: 116). In all, there are six colleges; namely, Guru Charan College, Cachar College, Radhamadhab College, Women's College, Teachers Training College and Silchar College of Education; a national technical institute- National Institute of Technology (NIT)- and a central university- Assam University (AU)- in the town. In these institutions students are drawn from both the urban and rural areas of the south Assam as well as other parts of Assam and the North East India (except Sikkim). NIT and AU also draw students from the states other than those of the northeastern region. The south Assam comprises five districts, comprising three plains districts; namely, Cachar, Hailakandy and Karimganj in the valley of the

Barak River and two hill districts; namely, Dima Hasao and Karbi Anglong. Rest of Assam comprises the valley of the river Brahmaputra. Other states in the region are Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura. In 2002 Sikkim has also been included in the region.

Socio-economic background of the respondents

Of the sampled rural female Muslim students in the higher educational institutions of the Silchar town, three fourths (75%) are from the colleges; about one fourth (24.31%) are from the university and a small fraction is from the National Institute of Technology. Over three fourths (76.39%) of the students are from Arts stream of studies, over one tenth from Science stream and a small fraction from Commerce stream.

Near about three fifths (58.33%) of the students belong to the age group of 18-20 while over one third (36.11%) belong to the age group of 21-23. Most (99.31%) of them are Sunni- the main religious sect of Islam in the Barak valley. Most (88.2%) of them belong to the General Class category; over one tenth (11.11%) belong to the Other Backward Classes (OBCs) category and a small fraction belong to the Most Other Backward Classes (MOBCs) category. Of the students 86.81% are Bengali.

The family occupation of nearly a half of the students (48.61%) is business, followed by service (30.56%), and the rest of the families have non-workers and those engaged with agriculture. About one third (32.64%) of the families have the annual income of Rs. 150001-200000/-, followed by Rs. 100001-150000/- (27.08%), indicating that majority of them are from middle income group.

Mobile phone access patterns among the respondents

The access to mobile phone among the students of low and middle income households is influenced by the factors like rural-urban location, age, occupation, household income and educational level. Need to communicate with family members and friends is the

key factor responsible for owning of the mobile phone among the students. A stratified random sample of 145 students was drawn from the female rural Muslim students. Out of these, one student did not have any mobile set and she did not access it. The mobile phone access patterns among the rest (144) of the students are given here.

Types of Mobile Connectivity Subscription

Among the students there are found two types of mobile connectivity subscription; namely, pre-paid and post-paid connectivity subscriptions which are also referred to as 'pay-as-you-talk' and 'alternative billing method' respectively. There are the cases of the students who are subscribers of both the pre-paid and the post-paid connectivity. The distribution of the respondents into the types of mobile connectivity subscription is given in the following table:

Table 1
 Types of Mobile Connectivity Subscription among the Respondents
 N=144

Type of Mobile Connectivity Subscription	No. of Respondents (%)
Pre-paid	136 (94.44)
Post-paid	10 (6.94)
Total	144(100%)

As the table reveals, most of the female students (94.44%) subscribe pre-paid mobile connectivity and the rest subscribe post-paid mobile connectivity. As they are dependent on their parents and get pocket money from their parents, they subscribe the pre-paid mobile connectivity to make limited number of phone calls and restrict their expenditure on mobile use.

Mobile Service Providers

The mobile service provider is referred to as the wireless service provider (WSP). Among the students, there are found two types of mobile service providers; viz., public (Government) sector WSP; namely, Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited (BSNL) and private sector WSPs; namely, Airtel, Aircel, Reliance, Vodafone, Idea and Tata Indicom. There are some respondents who take services from more than one mobile service provider. The following table exhibits the distribution of the students by their WSPs:

Table 2
Mobile Service Providers among the Respondents
N=144

Mobile Service Provider	No. of Respondents (%)
BSNL	47 (32.64%)
Airtel	38 (26.39%)
Aircel	23 (15.97%)
Reliance	20 (13.89%)
Vodafone	22 (15.28%)
Idea	2 (1.39%)
Tata Indicom	7 (4.86%)
Total	144(100%)

The table reveals that of the female students, about one third take the services from Bharat Sanchar Nigam Limited (BSNL)- the sole public sector mobile service operator, subsequently followed by the private sector mobile service providers, such as Airtel (26.39%), Aircel (15.97%), Vodafone (15.28%), Reliance (13.89%) and the rest are users of Tata Indicom and Idea. Thus, the dominant role is played by the public sector unit in the mobile network service in the Silchar town because it was the only service provider in the past.

Access to Mobile Features/ Facilities

The features on mobile phone are a set of services and applications offered by the mobile company to users. The students have access to 12 mobile architectural features; namely, telephone, SMS, MMS, dual SIM, audio player, video player, digital camera, FM radio, WAP, colouring set, black & white set and 3-G service. The following table depicts the distribution of the students by their access to mobile features:

Table 3
Access to Mobile Features/ Facilities among the Rural Female Muslim Students
N= 144

Access to Mobile Features/ Facilities	No. of Respondents (%)
Telephone	144 (100%)
SMS	144 (100%)
MMS	50 (34.72%)
Dual SIM	10 (6.94%)
Audio player	112 (77.78%)
Video player	112 (77.78%)
Digital camera	112 (77.78%)
FM radio	39 (27.08%)
WAP	112 (77.78%)
Colouring set	135 (93.75%)
Black & white set	9 (6.25%)
3-G service	12 (8.33%)

The data show that all the students make access to telephone and SMS on their mobile sets, followed by audio player, video player, digital camera and Wireless Application Protocol. The Frequency Modular Radio and 3-G services are also becoming popular among the students. It indicates that the students are not solely confined to access to the two principal mobile features;

viz., telephone and SMS; rather they access to multiple features and facilities of the mobile communication technology. Now-a-days, mobile phone is the convergence of different technological features which earlier functioned as individual technology. Attractive mobile features with audio-visual facilities are accessed by majority of the students.

Mode of Acquiring Mobile Phone

The way the students acquired a mobile phone set makes three categories; viz., purchased by oneself, purchased by family members (father, mother, brother, sister and uncle) and received as a gift. The distribution of the students into these categories is shown in the following table:

Table 4
 Mode of Acquiring Mobile Phone among the Respondents

Mode of Acquiring Mobile Phone	No. of Respondents (%)
Purchased by oneself	14 (9.72%)
Purchased by Family members (father, mother, brother, sister and uncle)	126 (87.5%)
Got it as a gift	4 (2.78%)
Total (%)	144 (100%)

The figures point out that for most (87.5%) of the students mobile phone was purchased by family members such as father, mother, brother, sister or uncle and the least of them purchased it themselves or received it as gift. It is because they are dependent on families.

Number of Incoming and Outgoing Calls Per Day

The phone call is an act of telephoning from someone to someone. Intensity of calls going out and coming in between two individuals shows density of interactions. The number of incoming and outgoing calls on mobile phone in a day is shown under four categories; namely, 1-5, 6-10, 11-15 and more than 15. The following table shows the distribution of the

respondents by the number of incoming and outgoing calls on their mobile sets:

Table-5:
 Number of Incoming and Outgoing Calls Per Day on Mobile Phone

Number of Calls	Incoming Calls on Mobile (Per Day)	Outgoing Calls on Mobile (Per Day)
	No. of Respondents (%)	No. of Respondents (%)
1-5	22 (15.28%)	0(0%)
6-10	75 (52.08%)	82 (56.94%)
11-15	41 (28.47%)	28 (19.44%)
> 15	6 (4.17%)	5 (3.48%)
Total (%)	144 (100%)	144 (100%)

The table shows that over a half (52.08%) of the students receive 6 to 10 calls in a day, over a quarter (28.47%) receive 11 to 15 calls per day, over one tenth (15.28%) receive 1 to calls daily and a few receive over 15 calls per day.

On the other hand, over a half (56.94%) of the students make 6 to 10 calls per day, followed by 11 to 15 calls (20.14%). Thus, contingent upon their economic conditions the students receive and make calls from and to their family members or others for necessary communication.

Incoming and Outgoing SMSs/ MMSs Per Day

The Short Message Service (SMS) is a text messaging service component of phone, web or mobile communication systems. The number of incoming and outgoing SMSs/MMSs on mobile phone in a day is also shown into four categories; namely, 1-5, 6-10, 11-15 and more than 15. The following table shows the number of incoming and outgoing SMSs/MMSs on mobile phone in a day among the female students:

Table 6
 Incoming and Outgoing SMSs/ MMSs Per Day on Mobile Phone

Number of SMSs/ MMSs	Incoming SMSs/ MMSs Per Day	Outgoing SMSs/ MMSs Per Day
	No. of Respondents (%)	No. of Respondents (%)
1-5	24 (16.67%)	24 (16.67%)
6-10	73 (50.69%)	82 (56.94%)
11-15	40 (27.78%)	29 (20.14%)
> 15	7 (4.86%)	9 (6.25%)
Total (%)	144 (100%)	144 (100%)

The table tells that half (50.69%) of the students receive 6 to 10 SMSs/ MMSs per day, subsequently followed by 11 to 15 SMSs (27.78%), 1 to 5 SMSs (16.67%) and over 15 SMSs (4.86%).

On the other hand, they send SMSs/ MMSs to friends, family members and others. Over a half (56.94%) of the students send 6 to 10 SMSs/ MMSs per day, subsequently followed by 11 to 15 SMSs (20.14%), 1 to 05 SMSs (16.67%) and over 15 SMSs/ MMSs.

Thus, they moderately receive and send SMSs/ MMSs as texting has become a much easier and cheaper way in which one can stay in touch with their friends and families, even they receive quick updates about after-college plans. The number of calls and SMSs/ MMSs indicates an intensive communication of the students on their mobile sets.

Results of the study

The results of the study are discussed hereunder.

All the rural female Muslim students but one have access to mobile phone. Owning a mobile phone has become a practical necessity as well as a status symbol for youth. The mobile handset has become a fashion accessory among them as they are the early adopters.

The pre-paid connection is convenient to the students as they recharge their mobile phones with different recharge cards and use it according to their requirement and convenience. The mobile phone is portable, for which it is more preferred to the landline telephone at home. All the students access to the phone and SMS services of their mobile sets.

The public (Government) sector service provider provides a range of services to people, especially in the remote, backward areas. Updated features of mobile phone with wireless application protocol are getting prominence among them. The rural/ urban residential factor has not come in the way of owning a mobile phone. The mobile phone is well-integrated into the students' day-to-day life as it is used for communication, learning, information retrieval and exchange, entertainment, and even for their household business.

Students who are generally dependent on their parents/ guardians get the mobile phones through family members and adopt mobile tools and applications to support their formal learning activities at educational institutions.

Majority of the female students receive as well as send as well as receive 6 to 10 calls and SMSs/ MMSs per day. As such they engage in intensive communication on their mobile sets, which definitely impact their the quality of interactions and interrelations.

Conclusion

The access to pre-paid mobile connection has significantly increased the affordability of mobile phone among the rural female Muslim students. Accessing mobile phone is not an economic constraint among them. They access to text messages more than phone calls in varying social situations. As they are mostly pre- paid mobile phone users, they tend to use text messaging service more than voice calls which is cheaper. Therefore, the significance and value of the mobile phone lies apparently in empowering women to communicate freely without the constraints of physical proximity and location specificity. There is needed a policy frame for use of mobile phone to increase literacy and learning among common and poor women in India as a way for their empowerment.

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